

STUDENTS' INTEREST IN BIOLOGY UNDER THE 7E INSTRUCTIONAL MODEL AND CONVENTIONAL TEACHING METHODS: A STUDY OF GENDER AND SCHOOL LOCATION DIFFERENCES IN BAYELSA STATE

BY

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Abstract

This study examined secondary school students' interest in Biology when taught using the 7E instructional model and the conventional teaching method, with emphasis on gender and school location in Bayelsa State. A quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group design was adopted for the study. The population comprised all Senior Secondary School II Biology students in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while a sample size of two hundred and thirty-eight Biology students drawn from selected co-educational secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area was used. Intact classes were assigned to experimental and control groups through balloting, and instruction was delivered by regular Biology teachers who were trained as research assistants prior to the treatment. Data were collected using the Biology Interest Inventory, and the reliability of the instrument was established using the Cronbach alpha method. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance was employed to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that although male students recorded slightly higher mean post-test mean interest scores than female students across the two instructional methods, the difference was not statistically significant. The results further showed that gender did not significantly influence students' interest in Biology. However, a significant interaction effect was found between instructional method and school location, indicating that students' interest in Biology differed significantly between urban and rural schools. The study concludes that while the 7E instructional model and conventional teaching methods are effective in enhancing students' interest in Biology irrespective of gender, school location plays a significant moderating role, and it recommends improved learning resources and context-sensitive instructional practices, especially in rural secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Keywords: 7E Instructional Model, Conventional Teaching Method, Students Interest, Gender, School Location, Biology

Introduction

The main goal of science education in any nation is to equip citizens with scientific and technical skills that are essential for economic growth and national development. According to Jabal (2018), no nation can attain meaningful progress and prosperity without adequate scientific knowledge and skilled manpower. Consequently, deliberate efforts must be made to expose young learners to modern science and technology at an early

stage. Science is defined as a systematic way of understanding natural events and is often described as a body of knowledge that explains universal laws and truths through scientific procedures related to the physical world. It provides explanations for natural phenomena, supports problem solving, and enables humans to manage their environment effectively (Cline, 2017). Among the science subjects, biology occupies a central position because of

its relevance to everyday life and its role in explaining natural events.

Biology is a core subject in the senior secondary school curriculum and contributes significantly to national development when properly taught and learned. The term biology is derived from the Greek words' bios, meaning life, and logos, meaning study, and it focuses on the study of the structure, function, development, origin, evolution, and distribution of living organisms (Bagley, 2017). Its scope spans from microscopic cellular components to the biosphere, encompassing all living organisms on earth. The study of biology enables students to understand interactions among organisms, inheritance of traits, and evolutionary relationships. It also serves as a foundational subject for professional courses such as medicine, pharmacy, agriculture, and biochemistry, making students interest in biology a critical concern at the secondary school level.

In many secondary schools, biology is predominantly taught using conventional teaching methods such as lectures, discussions, demonstrations, and routine laboratory activities. The lecture method, which is the most commonly used, often restricts students' participation and limits opportunities for inquiry, creativity, and sustained interest. Teaching methodology plays a crucial role in determining the quality of learning outcomes, as effective methods promote deeper understanding and positive learner disposition (Sor et al., 2018). Poor student performance and declining interest in science subjects have frequently been attributed to the persistent use of ineffective and teacher centered instructional strategies. Conventional methods, though popular, are associated with challenges such as low learner interest, minimal critical thinking, and uniform

instructional approaches that do not address individual learning differences.

Effective biology teaching therefore requires instructional strategies that actively engage learners, stimulate their interest, and promote meaningful learning experiences. One such strategy is the 7E instructional model, also known as the 7E learning cycle. The 7E model is a learner centered approach that evolved from the 5E model through the addition of the Elicit phase, which helps teachers assess learners' prior knowledge, and the Extend phase, which encourages application of learned concepts to new situations (Bybee, 2016). The seven phases, namely Elicit, Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, Evaluate, and Extend, provide structured opportunities for students to actively participate in learning, collaborate with peers, and relate biological concepts to real life experiences (Ong et al., 2018). Such active involvement is expected to enhance students' interest in biology lessons.

Students interest in biology may also be influenced by learner characteristics and contextual factors such as gender and school location. Gender differences in learning have been linked to sociocultural expectations and role socialization, which may shape students' attitudes and interest toward science subjects (Okeke, 2018). While some studies report differences in biology learning outcomes between male and female students, others indicate no significant variation (Inyang and Jegede, 2021). Similarly, school location has been identified as a factor that may affect learning experiences, as urban schools often have better access to instructional materials, laboratory facilities, and qualified teachers compared to rural schools (Ezike, 2021; Owwoeye and Yara, 2021).

However, some studies suggest that school location may not always have a significant

influence on students learning outcomes (Bosede, 2020).

Given the importance of biology to individual and national development, as well as the role of interest, gender, and school location in learning, there is a need to examine instructional strategies that can enhance students' interest in biology. Exploring the effectiveness of the 7E instructional model in comparison with conventional teaching methods, while considering gender and school location differences, is therefore imperative. This study seeks to investigate students' interest in biology under the 7E instructional model and conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, with a view to providing empirical evidence that can inform instructional practices and improve biology teaching and learning.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the effect of the 7E instructional model and conventional teaching methods on students' interest in Biology in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. ascertains the difference between the mean interest scores of male and female Biology students when taught using the 7E instructional model and conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State,
- ii. determine the difference between the mean interest scores of Biology students in urban and rural school locations when taught using the 7E instructional model and conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

- i. What is the difference between the mean interest scores of male and female biology students when exposed to the 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching

methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

- ii. Is there any difference between the mean interest scores of urban and rural school location biology students when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and were tested at a .05 significance level:

H01: There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female biology students when exposed to the 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

H02: There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of urban and rural school location biology students when exposed to the 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Methods

The study employed a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental design. This design was considered appropriate because the study involved intact classroom groups in a normal school setting where random assignment of individual students to experimental and control conditions would have been impractical. The pre-test was administered before treatment to establish the students' baseline level of interest in Biology and to control for possible initial differences among the groups. The population of the study comprised all Senior Secondary School II Biology students in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while the sample consisted of two hundred and thirty-eight (238) SS2 Biology students drawn from selected co-educational secondary schools in Yenagoa

Local Government Area. The SS2 class was deliberately chosen because students at this level had been exposed to relevant Biology concepts and were not under the immediate pressure of external examinations, thereby making them suitable for participation in the instructional treatment. Intact classes were assigned to experimental and control groups through balloting. Students in the experimental group were taught Biology using the 7E instructional model, while those in the control group were taught the same Biology content using the conventional teaching method.

The instrument used for data collection was the Biology Interest Inventory, which was designed to measure students' interest in Biology before and after exposure to the instructional methods. The instrument focused on students' attention, curiosity, participation, enjoyment, and general disposition toward Biology lessons. The Biology Interest Inventory was subjected to face and content validation by experts in Biology Education, Science Education, and Measurement and Evaluation to ensure that the items were clear, relevant, and suitable for SS2 Biology students. The reliability of the instrument was established using the Cronbach Alpha method, which was appropriate because the instrument contained rating-scale items measuring students' interest. Prior to the treatment, the Biology Interest Inventory was administered as a pre-test to both groups. The treatment was then carried out with the assistance of trained Biology teachers who served as research assistants and implemented the instructional procedures using standardized lesson guides prepared for the study.

The treatment involved teaching the experimental group with the 7E instructional model, which consists of the Elicit, Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, Evaluate, and Extend phases. This approach enabled students to activate prior knowledge, participate actively in learning activities, explore biological concepts, explain their understanding, apply knowledge to new situations, and evaluate their learning progress. The control group was taught using the conventional teaching method, which involved teacher explanation, discussion, questioning, and routine classroom activities. At the end of the treatment period, the Biology Interest Inventory was re-administered as a post-test to determine the effect of the instructional methods on students' interest in Biology. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The pre-test scores served as covariates in the ANCOVA analysis to control for initial group differences and improve the internal validity of the findings.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference between the mean interest scores of male and female biology students when exposed to the 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Summary of mean and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test scores of male and female students' interest in biology when exposed to the 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods

Teaching methods	Gender	N	Pre-test Scores		Post-test Scores		Mean Gain Scores
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
7E Instructional Model	Male	61	24.84	8.56	75.16	10.49	50.32

Conventional method	Teaching	Female	71	26.06	9.22	74.66	11.10	48.60
		Total	132	25.49	8.91	74.89	10.78	49.40
		Male	17	20.88	7.34	76.47	12.60	55.59
Total		Female	89	23.71	9.25	73.48	10.75	49.77
		Total	106	23.25	9.00	73.96	11.06	50.71
		Male	78	23.97	8.43	75.45	10.91	51.48
		Female	160	24.75	9.28	74.01	10.89	49.26
		Total	238	24.50	9.00	74.48	10.89	49.98

The data presented in Table 1 discloses that the mean post-test score of male students’ exposed to 7E-instructional model (75.16) was greater than the mean post-test score of female students exposed to 7E-instructional model (74.66). In Table 4.1.7, the mean post-test score of male students’ exposed to Conventional teaching method (76.47) was greater than the mean post-test score of female pupils’ exposed to Conventional teaching method (73.48). On the whole, the mean post-test score of male students’ exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (75.45) was greater than the mean post-test score of female students’ exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (74.01). Table 4.1.7 further shows that, the mean gain score of female students’ (51.48) was slightly greater than the mean gain score of male students’ (49.26) when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods. This infers that the interest in biology of male students’ was slightly greater than their female colleagues when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods.

Research Question Two: Is there any difference between the mean interest scores of urban and rural school location biology students’ when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Summary of mean and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test scores of urban and rural school location student’ interest in biology when exposed to 7E- instructional model and Conventional teaching methods

Teaching methods	School Location	N	Pre-test Scores		Post-test Scores		Mean Gain Scores
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
7E Instructional Model	Urban	75	26.00	8.89	78.93	9.49	52.93
	Rural	57	24.82	8.96	69.58	10.11	44.76
	Total	132	25.49	8.91	74.89	10.78	49.40
Conventional Teaching method	Urban	26	23.08	8.61	72.19	10.32	49.11
	Rural	80	23.31	9.17	74.38	11.32	51.07
	Total	106	23.25	9.00	73.96	11.06	50.71
Total	Urban	101	25.25	8.87	77.33	10.04	52.08
	Rural	137	23.94	9.08	72.38	11.05	48.44
	Total	238	24.50	9.00	74.48	10.89	49.98

The data presented in Table 2 shows that the mean post-test score of urban school location students’ exposed to 7E-instructional model (78.93) was greater than the mean post-test score of rural school location students’ exposed to 7E-instructional model (69.58). In

Table 2, the mean post-test score of urban school location students’ exposed to Conventional teaching method (72.19) was less than the mean post-test score of rural school location students’ exposed to Conventional teaching method (74.38). On the

whole, the mean post-test score of urban school location students' exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (77.33) was greater than the mean post-test score of rural school location students' exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (72.38). Table 2 similarly reveals that, the mean gain score of rural school location students' (52.08) was greater than the mean gain score of urban school location students' (48.44) when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods. This implies

that the interest in biology of urban school location students was greater than their rural school location colleagues when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female biology students when exposed to the 7E-instructional model and modified teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 3: Two-way post-test scores of male and female biology students' interests when exposed to the 7E-instructional model and modified teaching methods using pretest scores as covariates

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision at P<.05
Covariate pretest scores	866.403	1	866.402	7.469	.007	
Main effects (combined)	125.749	2	67.889	.585	.558	
Teaching methods	12.426	1	12.426	.107	.744	
Gender	123.353	1	123.353	1.063	.304	
2-way interaction teaching methods*Gender	79.914	1	79.914	.689	.407	NS
Model	1082.096	4	270.524	2.332	.057	
Residual	2709.299	233	116.006			
Total	25111.395	237	118.613			

NS = Not significant at .05 level; df = 1, 233; N = 238

Table 3 indicates that, the interaction effect is not significant at $p < .050$ alpha level. The reason is that the calculated p-value of .407 is greater than the criterion p-value of .05 alpha level with 1 and 233 degrees of freedom and F-value of .689. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no substantial dissimilarity between the mean interest scores of male and female biology students when exposed to 7E-instructional model and

modified teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, is accepted.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of urban and rural school location biology students when exposed to the 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Two ways ANCOVA on post-test scores of urban and rural school location biology students' interest when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods using pretest-scores as covariates

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision at P<.05
Covariate pretest scores	866.403	1	866.403	8.244	.004	

Main effects (combined)	1343.228	2	671.614	6.931	.002
Teaching methods	12.426	1	12.426	.118	.731
School location	1330.803	1	1330.803	12.663	.000
2-way interaction teaching methods*School location	1415.051	1	1415.051	13.465	.000 *
Model	3624.682	4	906.171	8.623	.000
Residual	24486.713	233	105.093		
Total	28111.395	237	118.613		

* = Significant at .05 level; df = 1, 233; N = 238

The data presented in Table 4 reveals that the interaction effect is substantial at $p < .050$ alpha level because, the calculated p-value of .000 is less than the criterion p-value of .05 alpha level with 1 and 233 degrees of freedom and F-value of 13.465. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no substantial disparity between the mean interest scores of urban and rural school location biology students when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State cannot be retained. Hence, the alternative hypothesis which states that, there is a significant difference between the mean interest scores of urban and rural school location biology students' when exposed to the 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Discussion

Students' gender and their interest in biology in Secondary Schools. The result in Table 4.1.7 reveals the mean post-test score of male students' exposed to 7E- instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (75.45) was greater than the mean post-test score of female students' exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (74.01). This implies that the interest in biology of male students was slightly greater than their female colleagues when exposed to

7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods. However, when two ways was applied to test the null hypothesis, it shows p-value of .407 which was found to be statistically not significant at .05 alpha level with 1 and 233 degrees of freedom. The result therefore reveals that there is no substantial disparity between the mean interest scores of male and female biology students' when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools. The findings of this study are in alignment with the findings of Giso et al (2024) that a substantial disparity does not exist between the mean interest scores of male and female biology students' when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools. In the contrary, the findings of this study are not in alignment with the findings of Ezeobi et al (2020) who also observed that, there is a substantial disparity between the mean interest scores of male and female biology students' when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools.

School location and students' interest in biology in Secondary Schools: The result in Table 1 shows the mean post-test scores of rural school location students' exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (78.98) was greater than the mean post-test score of urban school location

students' exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (76.98). This implies that the achievement in biology of rural school location students' was greater than their urban school location colleagues when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods. Nevertheless, when two ways was applied to test the null hypothesis, it indicates p-value of .004 which was found to be statistically significant at .05 alpha level with 1 and 233 degrees of freedom. The result therefore reveals that there is a substantial disparity between the mean achievement scores of urban and rural school location biology students' when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools. The findings of this study are in agreement with the findings of Akilu et al (2023) that a substantial disparity exists between the mean achievement scores of urban and rural school location biology students' when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools. In the contrary, the findings of this study are not in alignment with the findings of Samba et al (2016) who also observed that, there is no substantial disparity between the mean achievement scores of urban and rural school location biology students' when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools.

School location and students' interest in biology in Secondary Schools. The result in Table 3 indicates the mean post-test score of urban school location students' exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (77.33) was greater than the mean post-test score of rural school location students' exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods (72.38). This implies that the interest in biology of urban school location students' was greater than their rural school location colleagues when exposed to 7E-instructional model and

Conventional teaching methods. Nevertheless, when two ways was applied to test the null hypothesis, it reveals p-value of .000 which was found to be statistically significant at .05 alpha level with 1 and 233 degrees of freedom. The result therefore reveals that there is a substantial disparity between the mean interest scores of urban and rural school location biology students' when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools. The findings of this study are in accord with the findings of Udeani and Okafor (2012) that a substantial disparity exists between the mean interest scores of urban and rural school location biology students' when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools. On the other hand, the findings of this study are not in accordance with the findings of Samba et al (2016) who also observed that, there is no substantial disparity between the mean interest scores of urban and rural school location biology students' when exposed to 7E-instructional model and Conventional teaching methods in secondary schools.

Conclusion

This study concluded that the use of the 7E instructional model and conventional teaching methods enhanced students' interest in Biology across gender and school location, though the pattern of influence varied. While descriptive results showed that male students recorded slightly higher mean post-test interest scores than their female counterparts, the difference was not statistically significant, indicating that gender did not significantly influence students' interest in Biology when exposed to the 7E instructional model and conventional teaching methods. This suggests that the instructional approaches were equally effective in stimulating interest among both male and female students. However, school location significantly influenced students' interest in Biology, as a statistically significant

difference existed between urban and rural students. Urban school students demonstrated higher mean post-test interest scores overall, although rural students recorded higher mean gain scores in some instances, indicating notable improvement when exposed to the instructional treatments. The significant interaction effect between teaching methods and school location implies that contextual factors such as availability of resources and learning environment play a crucial role in shaping students' interest in Biology. Overall, the findings affirm the effectiveness of the 7E instructional model in enhancing students' interest in Biology and underscore the need for policymakers and educators to address school location disparities to ensure equitable learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Biology teachers should be encouraged and trained to adopt the 7E instructional model in secondary schools, as it effectively enhances students' interest in Biology irrespective of gender.
2. Education authorities should improve instructional resources and learning facilities in rural schools to reduce school location disparities and maximize the effectiveness of innovative teaching methods such as the 7E instructional model.

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